

On Performance Analysis of a Neutrosophic Bipolar Fuzzy and Texture-Based Model for COVID-19 Detection from Chest X-Rays

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Abstract. This study proposes a novel hybrid framework for rapid and accurate COVID-19 detection from chest X-ray images by integrating Neutrosophic Bipolar Fuzzy Sets (NBFS) with texture-based feature analysis. The methodology comprises four main stages: image acquisition, preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification. In the preprocessing phase, NBFS enhances image contrast by decomposing each image into positive, negative, and indeterminate components using intensity thresholds. The neutrosophic domain assigns truth, falsity, and indeterminacy values, enabling robust handling of noise and uncertainty in medical imaging. Texture features are extracted using the Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM), capturing spatial intensity relationships critical for distinguishing infected regions. These features are classified using Decision Tree, Logistic Regression, and k-Nearest Neighbour (k-NN) models. Experimental evaluations on a benchmark chest X-ray dataset demonstrate that the Decision Tree classifier outperformed other models, achieving an accuracy of 95.92%, sensitivity of 96.55%, and specificity of 95.30%. The proposed approach offers a fast, interpretable, and cost-effective diagnostic aid, potentially supporting large-scale screening in clinical settings. Future research will explore multi-class classification and application to diverse medical imaging modalities.

Keywords: COVID-19 detection; Chest X-ray; Neutrosophic Bipolar Fuzzy Set; Texture Analysis; Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM); Machine Learning; k-nearest Neighbors (k-NN); Logistic Regression; Decision Tree; Medical Image Processing.

1. Introduction

The global pandemic brought on by COVID-19 has resulted in significant morbidity and mortality. Prompt and precise identification of COVID-19 is essential for stopping the virus's transmission and guaranteeing prompt medical attention [1]. The most reliable method for diagnosing COVID-19 is RT-PCR, which detects RNA from the virus in patient samples. Nevertheless, RT-PCR is less useful for large-scale screening due to a number of drawbacks, such as lengthy processing times, high expenses, and possible false-negative rates [2, 3].

As an alternative, medical imaging methods have been widely used for COVID-19 identification, especially Xray imaging (CXR), computational tomography (CT). CT provides detailed body structure visualization and has shown high sensitivity for COVID-19 pneumonia detection. However, CT-scans are expensive, involve high radiation exposure, and are not readily available in all healthcare settings, especially in low-resource regions [4, 5]. On the other hand, CXR imaging is inexpensive, accessible, and a rapid diagnostic technique for COVID-19 screening. Bilateral lung opacities, ground-glass opacities, and consolidation are among the distinctive patterns seen in CXR images that have been shown in multiple investigations to be suggestive with COVID-19 infection [6, 7]. However, the subtle variations among COVID-19 pneumonia and other breathing-related conditions make manual interpretation of CXR images difficult, requiring automated image processing tools.

As machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) have advanced, there has been a lot of interest in automated COVID-19 diagnosis using CXR pictures. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), in particular, have been used extensively for CXR-based COVID-19 identification because of its capacity to extract hierarchical patterns from medical pictures [8]. Despite their excellent classification accuracy, CNN-based models need a lot of labeled data and a lot of processing power to train. Additionally, deep learning models' interpretability in clinical settings is limited by their "black-box" character [9]. Researchers have looked into texture-based feature extraction methods to overcome these obstacles. One such method is the GLCM, which finds statistical patterns in medical images. These handcrafted features provide interpretable insights into the spatial relationships between pixel intensities, enhancing the performance of traditional machine learning classifiers [10]. Another promising approach is the NBFS, which extends the traditional fuzzy set by incorporating truth, falsity, and indeterminacy values in a bipolar framework. This approach enhances uncertainty modeling and noise reduction in medical image analysis, making it particularly useful for CXR-based COVID-19 detection [11].

In this study, we use GLCM extraction of features and NBFS decomposition to present an effective and interpretable feature-based method for COVID-19 identification using chest scans. The method begins with image pre-processing, where the CXR images are resized, converted to

grayscale (if necessary), and normalized to enhance contrast and reduce noise. Next, the NBFS decomposition technique is applied, segmenting the images into three components—positive, negative, and indeterminate regions—to capture essential texture details while reducing uncertainty in medical image interpretation. From these decomposed images, GLCM features such as contrast, correlation, energy, and homogeneity are extracted to quantify texture variations associated with COVID-19 pneumonia. These characteristics are subsequently incorporated into machine learning classifiers that are trained to differentiate between COVID-19 alongside normal scenarios, such as Decision Tree models, Logistic Regression, and k-NN.

This hybrid technique is appropriate for real-time COVID-19 screening in clinical settings because it improves classification accuracy while maintaining interpretability. The suggested approach addresses important issues in automated COVID-19 detection and has a number of benefits over deep learning-based methods. First of all, it makes real-time applications possible in resource-constrained contexts by lowering computational complexity and doing away with the requirement for intensive training on big datasets. Second, the combination of NBFS and GLCM features enhances interpretability by offering valuable information on the textural characteristics of lungs impacted by COVID-19. This information can help radiologists make clinical decisions. Furthermore, even in low-quality X-ray pictures, the NBFS framework ensures dependable feature extraction by improving resistance to noise and uncertainty. By providing an affordable, easily available, and interpretable quick screening method, this study advances AI-driven COVID-19 diagnostic tools, which are essential for controlling outbreaks and lessening the effects of upcoming pandemics.

1.1. *Research Gap and Objectives*

Current automated techniques for detecting COVID-19 from chest X-ray pictures have a number of drawbacks, such as poor image contrast, noise sensitivity, and a lack of mechanisms to deal with image uncertainty in medical imaging. Additionally, even though many deep learning techniques achieve high accuracy, they are less useful in clinical settings with limited resources since they necessitate vast annotated datasets, significant processing resources, and frequently lack interpretability.

This paper suggests a hybrid framework that combines GLCM-based texture feature extraction for reliable picture representation with NBFS for improved contrast and uncertainty management in order to overcome these drawbacks. This work's primary goals are:

- 1 To develop NBFS-based preprocessing approach for improving the quality and diagnostic value of COVID-19 CXR images
- 2 To extract discriminative texture features capable of effectively differentiating COVID-19 cases from normal cases.

- 3 To compare and evaluate multiple machine learning classifiers to determine the most accurate and reliable model for clinical application.

1.2. Core Contributions

Despite advancements in automated COVID-19 detection, several persistent challenges remain in the use of chest X-ray (CXR) imaging. First, image quality varies significantly due to differences in acquisition devices and patient conditions, often resulting in low contrast and noise. Second, most conventional image processing methods are not equipped to manage uncertainty and ambiguity inherent in medical images. Third, deep learning-based models, although achieving high accuracy, demand large annotated datasets and considerable computational resources, which limits their applicability in resource-constrained clinical environments. Finally, many existing approaches lack interpretability, making it difficult for medical professionals to trust and validate automated diagnostic outcomes. These issues collectively underscore the need for robust, interpretable, and computationally efficient frameworks that can perform reliably on small to medium datasets.

- 1 **Novel preprocessing method** – An image enhancement strategy based on NBFS to improve contrast and effectively handle uncertainty in CXR images.
- 2 **Robust feature extraction** – Use of GLCM texture features to capture spatial intensity patterns relevant for COVID-19 detection.
- 3 **Comprehensive classifier evaluation** – Performance comparison of classifiers to identify the most accurate and reliable model.
- 4 **High diagnostic performance** – The suggested framework outperforms traditional techniques with an accuracy of 95.92%.
- 5 **Practical applicability** – The framework is interpretable, computationally efficient, and suitable for large-scale clinical screening in diverse healthcare environments.

2. Materials and Methods

This study uses machine learning classifiers and texture-based feature extraction to identify COVID-19 in chest imaging (CXR) images. Dataset selection, image preliminary processing, NBFS transformation, attribute extraction, and data classification are some of the crucial elements in the suggested methodology. Ensuring the accuracy and durability of the classification model requires each step.

The Kaggle database makes the dataset used in this investigation freely accessible. It consists of 392 CXR images, with an equal distribution of 196 normal (healthy) cases and 196 abnormal (COVID-19 positive) cases. By ensuring that the model generalizes effectively across Sanjayprabu S et.al., On Performance Analysis of a Neutrosophic Bipolar Fuzzy and Texture-Based Model for COVID-19 Detection from Chest X-Rays

various patient demographics and imaging situations, this balanced dataset helps to minimize bias in classification findings.

2.1. Methodology overview

The proposed framework follows a four-stage pipeline: (1) image acquisition and preprocessing, (2) NBFS-based image enhancement, (3) texture feature extraction using the GLCM, and (4) supervised classification and evaluation. There are 392 chest X-ray pictures in the experimental collection (196 COVID-19, 196 normal). A grid-search technique with 5-fold cross-validation was used to hyperparameter tune the training set; the hold-out test set is where the final performance metrics are presented..

2.2. Image Pre-Processing

To standardize the input images, various pre-processing techniques are applied:

- Grayscale Conversion: Since X-ray images inherently contain intensity variations, grayscale conversion is performed to reduce computational complexity while preserving essential texture details.
- Image Resizing: To guarantee uniformity during feature extraction, all photos are scaled to 256 by 256 pixels.
- Pixel Intensity Normalization: To boost classification performance and contrast, image value of pixels have been normalized to a range of 0 to 1.
- Noise Reduction: A median filter is used to eliminate unwanted noise, preserving crucial image details.

A sample of the dataset, illustrating normal and disease-affected images, is shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. Chest X-ray Normal Vs. Abnormal

2.3. Proposed Methodology

A structured pipeline combining image pre-processing, NBFS-based transformation, texture feature extraction, and machine learning classification is the suggested methodology for identification of COVID-19 using chest X-ray (CXR) pictures. The process begins with image acquisition, where CXR images are collected from publicly available medical imaging repositories, ensuring a balanced dataset of COVID-19-positive and normal cases. Pre-processing is performed to standardize the images, including grayscale conversion to reduce computational complexity, image resizing to 256×256 pixels for uniformity, and intensity normalization to enhance contrast and improve classification accuracy. After pre-processing, the NBFS transformation is applied to segment the image into three components: Positive (P), Negative (N), and Indeterminate (I).

This transformation enhances the contrast in crucial lung regions by modeling uncertainty and handling ambiguous intensity variations in the X-ray images. The Positive Component (P) highlights high-intensity regions linked to abnormal lung opacities, the Negative Component (N) represents normal lung areas, and the Indeterminate Component (I) manages uncertain pixel intensities. This segmentation technique improves feature extraction accuracy by preserving essential structural details in the lung regions. The GLCM, which is used for feature extraction, computes four statistical texture properties for each of the three image components: contrast, correlation, energy, and homogeneity. These texture descriptors capture significant textural variations, aiding in the differentiation between COVID-19-positive and normal cases. Ultimately, three ML models—employed to classify the retrieved feature vectors. F1-score, Accuracy, are used to assess the effectiveness of the classifiers, which are trained on 70% of the dataset and assessed on the remaining 30%. The integration of NBFS transformation with texture-based feature extraction enhances feature representation, ensuring optimal classification performance for COVID-19 detection from radiographic images.

2.4. Limitations of the proposed methodology

We explicitly acknowledge several limitations: (1) Parameter sensitivity — NBFS enhancement depends on threshold and weighting choices; while validated on our dataset, these may require retuning for new datasets. (2) Dataset size and generalizability — with 392 images, the model requires external validation on larger, multi-center datasets to confirm generalizability. (3) Handcrafted features vs deep learning — GLCM features are interpretable but may not capture all subtle patterns that end-to-end deep networks learn; however, our approach trades off large data requirements and opacity for interpretability and lower computational cost. (4) Single modality — results are for PA/AP chest X-rays only and may not transfer directly to Sanjayprabu S et.al., On Performance Analysis of a Neutrosophic Bipolar Fuzzy and Texture-Based Model for COVID-19 Detection from Chest X-Rays

CT images without adaptation. We discuss these limitations and propose mitigation strategies (parameter validation, external test sets, and hybrid extensions combining NBFS+texture features with deep features) in the Conclusion.

3. Neutrosophic Bipolar Fuzzy Set-Based Image Processing

NBFS-based image processing is an advanced computational technique that enhances the feature representation of medical images by decomposing them into three distinct components: Positive (truth) (P), Negative (Falsity) (N), and Indeterminate (I) [12]. This decomposition enables a more detailed analysis of Chest X-ray (CXR) images by distinguishing between different intensity regions, thereby enhancing COVID-19 detection precision. NBFS were selected because they explicitly model uncertainty and indeterminacy at the pixel level while allowing enhancement of relevant (positive) image components. This is particularly useful for CXR images where infection-related patterns may be subtle and corrupted by acquisition noise or low contrast.

3.1. NBFS Representation in Image Processing

Let $I(x, y)$ be the magnitude of a pixel at location (x, y) in the input image. Three membership functions are used to define the image's NBFS representation [13]:

- (1) **Truth-Membership Function** $T(x, y)$: Represents the probability of a pixel being part of an infected region (e.g., COVID-19 affected areas in CXR images).
- (2) **Falsity-Membership Function** $F(x, y)$: Represents the probability of a pixel being part of a normal (healthy) lung region.
- (3) **Indeterminacy-Membership Function** $I(x, y)$: Represents the uncertainty or ambiguity in classification.

A pixel in the NBFS-based image domain is represented as:

$$\text{NBFS}(I(x, y)) = (T(x, y), I(x, y), F(x, y)), \quad 0 \leq T, I, F \leq 1$$

where each function is defined as follows:

- **Truth Membership Function (T-MF):**

$$T(x, y) = \frac{I(x, y) - \min(I)}{\max(I) - \min(I)}, \text{ if } I(x, y) \geq T_1$$

where $\max(I)$ represent the max and min intensity values in the image. This function assigns high values to bright regions (potentially infected regions in X-ray images).

- **Falsity Membership Function (F-MF):**

$$F(x, y) = \frac{\max(I) - I(x, y)}{\max(I) - \min(I)}, \text{ if } I(x, y) \geq T_2$$

This function assigns high values to dark regions, corresponding to non-infected lung areas. •

Indeterminacy Membership Function (I-MF):

$$I(x, y) = 1 - (T(x, y) + F(x, y)), \text{ if } T_2 < I(x, y) < T_1$$

The indeterminate component captures the variations in texture and intensity caused by noise, structural overlaps, or mild infections that are difficult to classify. This function captures uncertainty in pixel classification, ensuring a smooth transition between infected and non-infected regions. The thresholds T_1 and T_2 are adaptively selected based on the image's histogram distribution, ensuring optimal separation between abnormal and normal regions.

3.2. Threshold Selection Using Otsu's Multi-Level Thresholding

Threshold selection is essential in NBFS-based segmentation, it determines cutoff points for infected and non-infected regions. The optimal thresholds T_1 and T_2 are obtained using Otsu's thresholding method, which minimizes intra-class variance. By the Otsu's thresholding principle, Let $P(i)$ be the probability that a pixel has intensity i , and let L be the total no. of magnitude levels in a picture. The picture's overall variance can be found using:

$$\sigma_T^2 = \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} P(i) (i - \mu_T)^2$$

where μ_T is the global average level of intensity:

$$\mu_T = \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} i \cdot P(i)$$

Finding the ideal threshold T that minimizes the intra-class variation is the aim of Otsu's method:

$$T = \arg \min_T [w_1(T) \sigma_1^2(T) + w_2(T) \sigma_2^2(T)]$$

where $\sigma_1^2(T)$ and $\sigma_2^2(T)$ are the variances of the two segmented classes, and $w_1(T)$ and $w_2(T)$ are their probabilities.

For a multi-level segmentation, we extend Otsu's method to obtain two thresholds T_1 and T_2 , separating the image into three regions (non-infected, uncertain, and infected):

$$(T_1, T_2) = \arg \min_{(T_1, T_2)} [w_1(T_1) \sigma_1^2(T_1) + w_2(T_1, T_2) \sigma_2^2(T_1, T_2) + w_3(T_2) \sigma_3^2(T_2)]$$

Where, w_1 corresponds to the non-infected region probability, w_2 corresponds to the uncertain (indeterminate) region, w_3 corresponds to the infected region.

The optimal thresholds are found iteratively by optimizing the variation across classes σ_B^2

$$\sigma_B^2 = \sigma_T^2 - [w_1(T) \sigma_1^2(T) + w_2(T) \sigma_2^2(T)]$$

This ensures that the segmentation effectively separates COVID-19 infected areas from normal lung regions while reducing classification errors.

3.2.1. Transformation of Image to NBFS Space

Once the The T_1 and T_2 criteria are established, the input image is transformed NBFS, where each pixel is assigned a tuple (T, I, F) . The final NBFS-transformed image is given by:

$$I_{\text{NBFS}}(x, y) = \{T(x, y), I(x, y), F(x, y)\}, \quad \forall(x, y) \in I$$

where $I_{\text{BNS}}(x, y)$ contains three independent layers representing truth (infected), falsity (non-infected), and indeterminacy (uncertainty).

Algorithm 1 NBFS Image Transformation

Require: Grayscale image $I(x, y)$, Thresholds T_1 and T_2

Ensure: Neutrosophic representation $I_{\text{NBFS}}(x, y) = \{T(x, y), I(x, y), F(x, y)\}$

```

1: Compute  $\min(I)$  and  $\max(I)$ 
2: for each pixel  $(x, y) \in I$  do
3:   if  $I(x, y) \geq T_1$  then
4:      $T(x, y) \leftarrow \frac{I(x, y) - \min(I)}{\max(I) - \min(I)}$ 
5:   else
6:      $T(x, y) \leftarrow 0$ 
7:   end if
8:   if  $I(x, y) \geq T_2$  then
9:      $F(x, y) \leftarrow \frac{\max(I) - I(x, y)}{\max(I) - \min(I)}$ 
10:  else
11:     $F(x, y) \leftarrow 0$ 
12:  end if
13:  if  $T_2 < I(x, y) < T_1$  then
14:     $I(x, y) \leftarrow 1 - (T(x, y) + F(x, y))$ 
15:  else
16:     $I(x, y) \leftarrow 0$ 
17:  end if
18: end for
19: return  $I_{\text{NBFS}}(x, y) = \{T(x, y), I(x, y), F(x, y)\}$ 

```

4. Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is a critical step in the purpose of identifying of COVID-19 with chest pictures. This work makes use of the GLCM, a widely used texture analysis method. to extract key characteristics from X-ray pictures that have been segmented. GLCM helps quantify the spatial relationships between pixel intensities, capturing texture patterns that differentiate normal lung tissues from COVID-19-affected regions

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4.1. Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix

GLCM determines the likelihood that two pixels in an image with distinct gray levels g_i and g_j , divided by certain distances d and direction θ , will have these colors. GLCM is provided mathematically by [13,14]:

$$P(i, j | d, \theta) = \frac{\text{Number of pixel pairs with values } (g_i, g_j)}{\text{Total number of pixel pairs at distance } d \text{ and angle } \theta}$$

where the probability of pixel intensity pairings (i, j) occurring at a specific distance and direction is denoted by $P(i, j)$. The extracted GLCM features provide essential texture information useful for classification. The key features used in this study are:

Contrast: Calculates the difference in intensity between adjacent pixels. Greater intensity variations are indicated by a higher contrast value, which is frequently observed in infected lungs due to irregular opacities.

Correlation: Establishes the statistical correlation between the intensities of the pixels. It calculates the correlation between each pixel and its neighbor throughout the whole image.

Energy: Energy, also referred to as Angular Second Moment (ASM), measures an image's textural homogeneity. A more homogeneous or uniform texture is implied by a higher energy value.

Homogeneity: Evaluates how closely the GLCM diagonal and the element distribution are related. Smooth textures are indicated by greater values when the gray levels of nearby pixels are comparable.

In chest X-ray pictures, GLCM-based texture features offer vital information for disease identification. The computed features help ML models differentiate between normal and infected lung tissues based on texture variations. The next section will discuss the classification techniques used for COVID-19 diagnosis using these extracted features.

Here is Table 1, which presents the extracted GLCM feature values for the Positive (P), Negative (N), and Indeterminate (I) components for both Normal and COVID-19 (Abnormal) cases.

TABLE 1. GLCM feature values for the Positive (P), Negative (N), and Indeterminate (I) components for both Normal and Abnormal cases

Features	Positive Component		Negative Component		Indeterminate Component	
	Normal	Abnormal	Normal	Abnormal	Normal	Abnormal
Contrast	1.78776	1.10554	1.21739	0.93515	2.97056	2.00164
Correlation	0.91987	0.88271	0.92830	0.90213	0.87139	0.90084
Energy	0.50569	0.60457	0.62808	0.74386	0.47238	0.54127
Homogeneity	0.96808	0.98026	0.97826	0.98330	0.94695	0.96426

Algorithm 2 GLCM Feature Extraction from NBFS Components

-
- 1: **Start**
 - 2: Load the NBFS transformed image.
 - 3: Extract the three components: Positive (T), Negative (F), and Indeterminacy (I).
 - 4: Define GLCM offsets (e.g., $[0, 1]$, $[1, 0]$, $[1, 1]$, $[-1, 1]$).
 - 5: Compute Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrices (GLCMs):
 - GLCM_T from Positive Component T
 - GLCM_F from Negative Component F
 - GLCM_I from Indeterminacy Component I
 - 6: Extract GLCM Features:
 - From GLCM_T: T_{Contrast} , $T_{\text{Correlation}}$, T_{Energy} , $T_{\text{Homogeneity}}$
 - From GLCM_F: F_{Contrast} , $F_{\text{Correlation}}$, F_{Energy} , $F_{\text{Homogeneity}}$
 - From GLCM_I: I_{Contrast} , $I_{\text{Correlation}}$, I_{Energy} , $I_{\text{Homogeneity}}$
 - 7: Construct the Feature Vector:

$$G = [T_{\text{Contrast}}, T_{\text{Correlation}}, T_{\text{Energy}}, T_{\text{Homogeneity}}, F_{\text{Contrast}}, F_{\text{Correlation}}, F_{\text{Energy}}, F_{\text{Homogeneity}}, I_{\text{Contrast}}, I_{\text{Correlation}}, I_{\text{Energy}}, I_{\text{Homogeneity}}]$$
 - 8: Save feature vector G for further classification or analysis.
 - 9: **End**
-

5. Classification

Following GLCM feature extraction, three supervised ML classifiers— are used for classification in order to differentiate between normal and COVID-19 (abnormal) situations. Each image is assigned to either the normal or COVID-19 class by these classifiers after they have examined the derived feature values. Each classifier's performance is assessed using common metrics such as accuracy, precision and etc.

5.1. *K*-Nearest Neighbors

An instance-based learning technique called the k-NN classifier uses the feature space's K nearest neighbors' majority vote to classify a fresh sample [15]. Finding the closest neighbors involves calculating the distance in Euclidean terms between each training sample x_i and a test sample x' using

$$d(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}_i) = \sqrt{\sum_{m=1}^M (x'_m - x_{i,m})^2}$$

where the total number of features is represented by M ., and x'_m and $x_{i,m}$ denote the m -th feature values of the test and i -th training sample, respectively.

The major-class label its K nearby neighbors is then applied to the test sample \mathbf{x}' :

$$y' = \text{mode}(y_i \mid \mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{N}_K(\mathbf{x}'))$$

where the set of K nn of the sample \mathbf{x}' is represented by $\mathcal{N}_K(\mathbf{x}')$.

The performance of the classifier is greatly impacted by the selection of K . Overfitting could result from a tiny K , which would capture noise in the training data., whereas a large K can improve generalization but may misclassify samples near class boundaries. A straightforward, non-parametric, and efficient classification algorithm, KNN works best with small datasets. However, because distances to all training samples must be calculated, it becomes computationally costly for large datasets.

5.2. Decision Tree

This classifier is a hierarchical model that recursively splits the dataset based on feature values [16]. The tree chooses the feature with the lowest Gini impurity or the biggest information gain at each node. Calculating the Gini impurity is done as

$$Gini(D) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^C p_i^2$$

where p_i is the likelihood that a sample is a member of class i , and C is the number of classes. A purer node is indicated by a lower Gini index.

Another commonly used criterion is entropy, which quantifies the level of disorder in a dataset:

$$H(D) = - \sum_{i=1}^C p_i \log_2(p_i)$$

The feature that results in the highest Information Gain (IG) is chosen for splitting. Information gain is calculated as:

$$IG(D, F) = H(D) - \sum_{v \in V} \frac{|D_v|}{|D|} H(D_v)$$

where V is the set of possible values of feature F , D is the current dataset, F is the feature under consideration, and D_v is the data subset that corresponds to value v . The entropy of the subset D_v is $H(D_v)$.

Decision trees are simple to understand and intuitive. They can handle both numerical and categorical data and are computationally efficient. However, if the tree grows too deep or if pruning techniques are not used, they are susceptible to overfitting.

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5.3. Logistic Regression

A statistical model for binary classification, logistic regression yields a likelihood number ranging from 0 and 1 [17]. The following is the outcome of using the sigmoid function to illustrate the relationship between the independent variables (features) and the dependent variable (like COVID-19 status):

$$P(Y = 1 | \mathbf{X}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{X} + b)}}$$

where $P(Y = 1 | \mathbf{X})$ is the probability that the sample is categorized as COVID-19 positive, b is the bias term, \mathbf{X} is the feature vector, and \mathbf{w} is the weight vector.

The decision is made by applying a threshold T , typically set to 0.5:

$$\hat{y} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } P(Y = 1 | \mathbf{X}) > T \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The two-dimensional cross-entropy loss function is minimized via logistic regression to get the model parameters:

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(P_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - P_i)]$$

where P_i is the expected probability for sample i , N is the total number of samples, and $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ is the true class label.

Real-time clinical decision-making can benefit from the computational efficiency and interpretability of logistic regression. However, it assumes linear separability between classes and may under perform on complex, non-linear datasets without additional feature engineering or transformations. After extracting GLCM features from the NBFS, the next step is classification.

Algorithm 3 K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) Classifier

1: **Start**2: Load the feature vector F and corresponding class labels Y .3: Define the number of neighbors K .4: Divide the dataset $(F_{\text{train}}, Y_{\text{train}})$ and $(F_{\text{test}}, Y_{\text{test}})$.5: **Training Phase**

6: Store the training feature vectors and their corresponding class labels.

7: **Classification Phase**8: **for** each test sample $X_{\text{test}} \in F_{\text{test}}$ **do**9: Compute the Euclidean distance between X_{test} and all training samples:

$$d(X_{\text{test}}, X_i) = \sqrt{\sum_{m=1}^M (x_m^{\text{test}} - x_{i,m})^2}$$

10: Identify the K nearest neighbors with the smallest distances.11: Assign the class label to X_{test} based on majority voting.12: **end for**13: **Performance Evaluation**14: Compute performance matrices using Y_{test} and predicted labels.15: **End**

Algorithm 4 Logistic Regression (LR) Classifier

1: **Start**2: Load the feature vector F and corresponding class labels Y .3: Divide the dataset $(F_{\text{train}}, Y_{\text{train}})$ and $(F_{\text{test}}, Y_{\text{test}})$.4: **Train Logistic Regression Model**5: Initialize model parameters: weights \mathbf{w} and bias b .6: **repeat**

7: Compute the sigmoid activation:

$$P = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{X} + b)}}$$

8: Compute binary cross-entropy loss:

9: Update parameters using gradient descent.

10: **until** convergence criteria is met11: **Classification (Testing Phase)**12: **for** each test sample $X_{\text{test}} \in F_{\text{test}}$ **do**

13: Compute probability using sigmoid function.

14: Assign class:

$$\hat{y} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } P \geq 0.5 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

15: **end for**16: **Performance Evaluation**

17: Compute performance matrices.

18: **End**

Algorithm 5 Decision Tree Classifier

```

1: Start
2: Load the feature vector  $F$  and corresponding class labels  $Y$ .
3: Divide the dataset  $(F_{\text{train}}, Y_{\text{train}})$  and  $(F_{\text{test}}, Y_{\text{test}})$ .
4: Build Decision Tree
5: Select the best feature for splitting using Gini Index or Information Gain.
6: Create branches based on feature values.
7: Repeat splitting recursively until:
    • Leaf nodes are pure, or
    • There is a meeting of a stopping requirement (such as minimum samples per node
      or maximum depth).
8: Classification (Testing Phase)
9: for each test sample  $X_{\text{test}} \in F_{\text{test}}$  do
10:   Traverse the tree from root to leaf using feature values.
11:   Assign predicted class based on the leaf node reached.
12: end for
13: Performance Evaluation
14: Compute accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.
15: End

```

6. Result and Discussion

Using the recovered GLCM-based texture features, the suggested COVID-19 detection model's performance was assessed using chest X-ray pictures. Three classification techniques were used to differentiate between normal and COVID-19-infected cases: Key performance indicators, including as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, were used to examine the results [18].

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{True-Positives} + \text{True-Negatives}}{\text{Total No. of Predictions}}$$

FP are normal cases that are mistakenly classified as disease, FN are diseased cases that are mistakenly classed as normal, True Negatives are normal cases that are appropriately categorized as negative, whereas True Positives are diseased cases that are appropriately labeled as positive. Precision measures the percentage of expected positive instances that are actually COVID-19. It is supplied by

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True-Positives}}{\text{True-Positives} + \text{False-Positives}}$$

while recall, which measures how many actual COVID-19 cases were correctly predicted, is given by

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True-Positives}}{\text{True-Positives} + \text{False-Negatives}}$$

The F1-score, which offers a fair assessment of recall and precision, is determined as

$$\text{F1-score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

FIGURE 2. NBFS Image Decomposition of a Chest X-ray

In the above Figure 2. The original grayscale image (top left) is decomposed into three components: Positive Component P (top right), Negative Component N (bottom left), and Indeterminacy Component I (bottom right). These components highlight different intensity-based features for texture analysis in medical image processing.

FIGURE 3. NBFS Image of a Chest X-ray Normal Vs. Abnormal

Figure 3. depicts the Neutrosophic Bipolar Image of a CXR Normal and Abnormal image.
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FIGURE 4. Scatter Plot for the A) KNN B) Decision Tree C) Logistic Regression classifiers

Figure 4. depicts the scatter plot of the KNN, Decision Tree, and Logistic Regression classifiers with the GLCM feature-vectors of the CXR images.

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FIGURE 5. Confusion Matrix for the A) KNN B) Decision Tree C) Logistic Regression classifiers

Figure 5 depicts the confusion matrix of the KNN, Decision Tree, and Logistic Regression classifiers with the GLCM feature vectors of the CXR images.

TABLE 2. Performance Comparison of Classification Algorithms

Features	KNN	Decision Tree	Logistic Regression
Sensitivity	83.33	96.55	90.73
Specificity	94.44	95.30	93.01
Accuracy	88.10	95.92	91.84
Error Rate	11.90	4.08	8.16
Precision	95.24	95.24	93.20
F1 Score	88.89	95.89	91.95
Jaccard Metric	80.00	92.11	85.09
Balanced Classifier Rate	88.89	95.93	91.87
Matthews Corr. Coefficient (MCC)	76.98	91.85	83.70

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The Table 2 shows the performance analysis of the KNN, Decision Tree, and Logistic Regression classifiers. Table 3 shows the comparison of the Existing Neutrosophic-Based Methods.

FIGURE 6. Performance Analysis of Classifiers

TABLE 3. Comparison of Proposed Method with Neutrosophic

Method	Technique	Features	Classifier	Accuracy (%)
Khalifa et al. (2020) [19]	Indeterminacy (I) neutrosophic domain	Deep Transfer Models (AlexNet/GoogLeNet/ResNet18)	AlexNet (best)	87.10
Khan et al. (2020) [20]	None (Deep CNN)	Xception-based features	CoroNet	89.60
Proposed work	NBFS (Bipolar)	GLCM texture features	Decision Tree / LR / k-NN	95.92

7. Conclusion

NBFS-based thresholding and GLCM texture feature extraction is used to assess the classification performance of suggested COVID-19 detection framework. Three machine learning classifiers were used: k-NN, Decision Tree, and Logistic Regression. According to the trial data, the Decision Tree classifier outperformed KNN (88.10%) and Logistic Regression (91.84%) by achieving the best accuracy of 95.92%.

A thorough examination of specificity and sensitivity revealed that the Decision Tree model exhibited superior COVID-19 detection capability, achieving the highest sensitivity (96.55% which indicates its strong ability to correctly identify COVID-19-positive cases). In contrast, Logistic Regression attained a sensitivity of 90.73%, while KNN lagged at 83.33%, making it less reliable for identifying infected patients. On the other hand, specificity, which measures the classifier's ability to correctly identify normal (non-COVID) cases, was highest for KNN (94.44%) and Decision Tree (95.30%), confirming their robustness in distinguishing between COVID and normal cases.

The error rate analysis further reinforced the Decision Tree's superior performance, as it had the lowest error rate of 4.08%, compared to Logistic Regression (8.16%) and KNN (11.90%), establishing it as the most dependable model for use in clinical settings. The precision-values were also consistently high across all classifiers, with Decision Tree and KNN achieving 95.24%, while Logistic Regression attained 93.19%, demonstrating their reliability in correctly predicting COVID-19-positive cases.

Additionally, the Decision Tree's effectiveness in feature-based categorization was validated by the F1-score and Jaccard Metric, which assess the trade-off between precision and recall, with respective values of 95.89% and 92.10%. Additionally, the Balanced Classifier Rate (BCR) of 95.93% and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) of 91.85% further supported the Decision Tree's robustness in handling the dataset with minimal bias toward either class.

The experimental findings highlight the impact of integrating NBFS-based thresholding with GLCM feature extraction in improving COVID-19 detection accuracy. Unlike conventional thresholding techniques, NBFS effectively handles uncertainty in medical images by refining contrast variations and enhancing critical features necessary for classification. This pre-processing approach allows machine learning models to extract meaningful texture-based patterns that differentiate COVID-19-infected lungs from normal ones, thereby improving classification accuracy. Although Logistic Regression performed reasonably well in balancing sensitivity and specificity, its relatively higher error rate suggests it might not be the ideal option for practical diagnostic uses. The KNN classifier exhibited lower performance, likely due to its sensitivity to feature distribution and reliance on neighbourhood-based distance metrics, which may not be optimal for high-dimensional medical imaging data.

Overall, these results validate the effectiveness of NBFS-based image pre-processing in combination with GLCM feature extraction for COVID-19 detection. The Decision Tree classifier emerged as the most reliable model, demonstrating high classification accuracy, low error rate, and strong performance across all evaluation metrics. Future research can further enhance this framework by exploring deep learning-based feature extraction, multimodal imaging integration (such as CT scans alongside X-rays), and hybrid models that combine traditional

machine learning with neural networks to achieve even higher diagnostic accuracy and reliability in COVID-19 detection.

8. Limitations and Future Work

Although the proposed NBFS–GLCM–classifier framework demonstrates competitive performance for There are a few limits to using CXR pictures for illness identification. Datasets of limited size and diversity that were made publically available were used for the study. Such datasets may not fully capture real-world variability in imaging conditions, patient demographics, and comorbidities. Therefore, it is still necessary to confirm the suggested approach’s generalizability to other clinical settings.

The study considered only three conventional classifiers for performance comparison. While these models provide interpretability, they may not exploit the full potential of the extracted features. Integration with more advanced classifiers, such as ensemble learning or lightweight deep neural networks, could yield further gains.

Future work will aim to (i) evaluate the proposed method on large-scale, multi-institutional datasets to establish clinical applicability; (ii) investigate hybrid feature extraction by combining texture descriptors (e.g., LBP, wavelets) with NBFS-enhanced GLCM; (iii) integrate explainable AI techniques to improve model transparency for clinical adoption; and (iv) explore real-time deployment in point-of-care settings, potentially influencing early screening protocols and decision support systems in radiology.

By addressing these limitations, the proposed approach could contribute to more reliable, interpretable, and widely deployable AI-assisted diagnostic tools for respiratory disease detection.

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